

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Section 2: Data Collection

Michelle C. Haas¹, Bettina B. Sommer¹, Simon van Rekum², Felix Moerman³, Eveline S. Graf¹

¹ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, School of Health Sciences

² ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, University Library

³ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, President's Office

1. Metadata

The following metadata should be collected when collecting data for each participant separately. For better reproducibility, having more personal data is beneficial. This results in ethical and legal issues, however, when sharing these data publicly. You must therefore clarify within your institution how much, and which, personal information is to be documented.

Table 1: Metadata that should be collected during data collection.

Title	Content/Format	Comment
Participant-specific information		
Identification number		Must be encoded or anonymous
Age	[Years]	
Gender or sex (depending on the study context)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Female • Male • Diverse 	
Height	[m]	2 decimal points
Weight	[kg]	2 decimal points
Leg length	[m]	2 decimal points
General information		
Date of data collection	[YYYY-MM-DD]	According to International Organization for Standardization 8601
Software(s) used for data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Manufacturer • Version • Type of data which were collected • Data format of the raw data (xcp, etc.) 	Please describe the type of data which were collected in the following form: sensor type and primary outcome of the research. Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marker-based kinematics • Sensor-based kinematics • Video-based (markerless) kinematics • Surface EMG • Force plate kinetics • Spatiotemporal parameters

Hardware which was used for data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Manufacturer • Type of data which were collected • Number and model of measurement device • Type and date of last calibration of hardware • If applicable: electrode material, shape, size • If applicable, measurement modes added to the accelerometer and gyroscopes in IMU's (e.g. magnetometer) 	<p>Please describe the type of data which were collected in the following form: sensor type and primary outcome of the research.</p> <p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marker-based kinematics • Sensor-based kinematics • Video-based (markerless) kinematics • Surface EMG • Force plate kinetics • Spatiotemporal parameters
Measurement frequency	[Hz]	For each measurement system separately, if not identical
Range of sensor (if applicable)	The range of values a sensor can measure. For accelerometers the range is reported in units of g (=9.8m/s ²)	
Study-specific inclusion and exclusion criteria	List of inclusion criteria List of exclusion criteria	<p>Please list all criteria that were defined during study design (a priori)</p> <p>If an ethics proposal had to be submitted, please list the same inclusion and exclusion criteria in this section.</p>
Description of tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of tasks including description of how they were performed • Naming convention/ meaning of the abbreviations in the file names <p>Randomization of task order (yes/no)</p>	<p>If walking or running was performed: indicate gait speed</p> <p>If EMG was measured: refer to the CEDE-Check for information of what to report regarding the task (Besomi et al., 2024)</p>

Sensor/probe placement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> List of placed sensors/probes including specific location and orientation of sensor/probe If applicable: interelectrode distance If applicable: sensor cap type 	If sEMG data is collected, use SENIAM guidelines to report sensor location and orientation. Refer to Standards for Reporting EMG Data https://isek.org/emg-standards/ (Merletti, 1999) and the CEDE-Checklist_(Besomi et al., 2024). Technical guidelines for ultrasound can be found on the essr website
Amplification of device (if applicable)		Please only describe discrete values
Calibration file (If available)	File where calibration values are exported before data collection	Please provide the corresponding file as csv
Calibration pose for subject-specific model (if applicable)	Which pose was used for calibration e.g. T-Pose, N-Pose	More information on subject-specific kinematic model calibration with IMU's can be found in Cereatti et al. (2024).
Electrode-Skin Impedance (if applicable)	[Ω]	2 decimal points
Signal-to-noise ratio (if applicable)	<p>General definition:</p> $\frac{\text{Power of the signal}}{\text{Power of background noise}}$ <p>Example for EMG:</p> $\frac{\text{EMG signal during muscle contraction}}{\text{unwanted electrical signal during muscle at rest}}$	2 decimal points
Mode of measurement device (if applicable)	<p>Example for ultrasound (depending on the device):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> amplitude mode brightness mode motion mode pulsed wave doppler mode etc. <p>Example for IMU :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> logging 	Technical guidelines for ultrasound can be found on the essr website

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • streaming 	
Dynamic range of measurement device (if applicable)	[dB]	2 decimal points
Penetration depth (if applicable)	[m]	2 decimal points
Preparation of the subject (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin preparation (shaving, application of alcohol, gel, etc.) 	
Reference electrode (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specify which electrode was chosen as the reference 	
Synchronisation method within a measurement device	Describe how multiple units of the same measurement device were synchronised.	
Synchronisation method for multiple measurement devices (if applicable)	<p>Describe how multiple devices were synchronised:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is the sampling frequency equal? If not, how is the data re-sampled? • Trigger signal (how is the delay determined?) • Time stamp • Post-processing synchronisation: align signals based on a point of interest (e.g. peak) 	
Image resolution (if applicable)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field of view [m] 	2 decimal points
Potential influencing factors on quality of measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Noise • Bias • Environmental factors • Etc. 	

The clinical movement analysis society of UK and Ireland defined standards in a clinical setting which can be used as a guide what information should additionally be reported on data collection (Stewart et al., 2023).

2. Marker model

When data is collected with a marker-based measurement system, it is important for the traceability and subsequent use of the data to have a clear understanding of the marker placement. The following information should be collected for later and then be published in a repository together with the data.

- Name of the marker model
- If available: Reference to the marker model
- List of all markers
 - Abbreviation of the marker
 - Name of the segment
 - Explanation of the marker placement; if the marker is placed on a plate / stick, please explain positioning of the marker plate / stick
- Anonymized photo of a participant with attached markers from anterior, posterior and lateral

2.1 Example:

Name: Conventional Gait Model (CGM) for lower extremities (Leboeuf et al., 2019), available from <https://pycgm2.netlify.app/ressources/palpation/>

Marker name	Body structure/segment	Palpation and placement
LASI / RASI	Left / Right Anterior Superior Iliac spine	Palpate from distal, most prominent projection medial.
LPSI / RPSI	Left / Right Posterior Superior Iliac spine	Palpate from distal, bony prominence directly over iliosacral recesses (visible in some people).
LTHI / RTHI	Left / Right Thigh	$\frac{1}{2}$ down lateral thigh. The anterior-posterior position is decisive. Not on the muscle belly of the vastus lateralis. Aligned in the plane so that the marker contains the hip and knee joint centres and the lateral femoral epicondyle.
LTHAP / RTHAP	Left / Right Thigh	$\frac{1}{3}$ of the way down to the centre of the anterior thigh (femur length defined from the ASIS to the epicondyle)
LTHAD / RTHAD	Left / Right Thigh	$\frac{2}{3}$ of the way down to the centre of the anterior thigh (femur length defined from the ASIS to the epicondyle)
LKNE / RKNE	Left / Right Knee Lateral Epicondyle	While the participant is standing with the knees in a neutral position, palpate the fibula head, move upwards and cross the joint line. The lateral femoral epicondyle is then approximately one finger width forward. Place the marker on the most prominent aspect.
LKNM / RKNM	Left / Right Knee Medial Epicondyle	While the participant is standing with the knees in a neutral position, follow the femur distally along the most distal third of the medial femur until you feel the adductor tubercle. The small bony prominence

Marker name	Body structure / segment	Palpation and placement
		approximately one thumb width distally and half a thumb width anteriorly is the medial epicondyle. Place the marker on the most prominent aspect.
LTIB / RTIB	Left / Right Tibia	Place the marker on ½ of tibia aligned in the plane so that the marker contains the knee and ankle joint centres and the flexion/extension axis of the upper ankle joint. As a rule, the axis of the upper ankle joint between the medial and lateral malleolus is rotated outwards by 5°-15° in relation to the flexion axis of the knee joint. The placement of the marker should reflect this.
LTIAP / RTIAP	Left / Right Tibia	Tibial tubercle (prominence on the superior anterior tibia). The marker is placed 2cm distal to the prominence of the tibial tubercle.
LTIAD / RTIAD	Left / Right Tibia	½ down the lower leg on the crest of the tibia.
LANK / RANK	Left / Right Ankle	Malleolus lateralis, most prominent point, along an imaginary line running through the transmalleolar axis.
LMED / RMED	Left / Right Ankle	Malleolus medialis, most prominent point, along an imaginary line running through the transmalleolar axis.
LHEE / RHEE	Left / Right Heel	On the posterior calcaneus at the most prominent aspect. Use the calliper to determine the height.
LTOE / RTOE	Left / Right Toe	On the back of the foot above the head of metatarsal II in the center from medial to lateral.
LVMH / RVMH	Left / Right Foot	On the line of metatarsal V (dorsal aspect) lateral to the extensor digitorum longus tendon.
LFMH / RFMH	Left / Right Foot	On the line of the metatarsophalangeal joint I (dorsal aspect), medial to extensor hallucis longus tendon
LSMH / RSMH	Left / Right Foot	on the line of the metatarsophalangeal joint II, center of the bone (medial to lateral)

3. Informed consent with reference to data sharing

3.1 Resources of swissethics

Swissethics provides a decision tree for finding the right template. The templates can be downloaded directly through the links provided in the decision tree. The decision tree can be found at https://swissethics.ch/assets/other_study_documents/decision-tree_v2.0_28.06.22_en.pdf or the German, French or Italian version at <https://swissethics.ch/templates> . If you are re-using data, you have to choose “No” in the first question “Is the research project a project involving living persons?” to get to the correct follow-up questions. Also, at <https://swissethics.ch/templates> you will find more templates in the national languages of Switzerland, e.g. for informed consent.

As is stated in the swissethics template for submitting a “Further use with consent” project as per HRA chapter 4 and HRO chapter 3: “For the further use of coded, health-related personal data (HRA Art. 32), the right of objection is sufficient.” Patients do not therefore have to give explicit consent. General consent from the patient is also possible. A template for general consent can be found at <https://swissethics.ch/documents/generalkonsent>.

3.1.1 *Example text for informed consent forms for encoded data*

Example text for informed consent forms in German, French, and Italian for encoded data can be found in the swissethics templates at <https://swissethics.ch/en/templates/studieninformationen-und-einwilligungen>

Please refer to these templates and pay special attention to the sections on data processing, encoding, data protection, and data protection for further use!

4. References:

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